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1. Introduction

The European Human Exposome Network combines nine research Projects funded under Horizon 2020, the EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation, call SC1-BHC-28-2019: “The Human Exposome Project: a toolbox for assessing and addressing the impact of environment on health”. These nine Projects are listed below:

- **ATHLETE** - Advancing tools for human early life-course exposome research and translation
- **EPHOR** - Exposome Project for health and occupational research
- **EQUAL-LIFE** - Early environmental quality and life course mental health effects
- **EXIMIOUS** - Mapping exposure induced immune effects: connecting the exposome and the immunome
- **EXPANSE** - Exposome powered tools for healthy living in urban settings
- **HEAP** - Human exposome assessment platform
- **HEDIMED** - Human exposomic determinants of immune mediated diseases
- **LONGITOOLS** - Dynamic longitudinal exposome trajectories in cardiovascular and metabolic non communicable diseases
- **REMEDIA** - Impact of exposome on the course of lung diseases

The human exposome encompasses exposures to environmental factors (elements we are exposed to via our diet, lifestyle and the environment we live and work in) throughout life, starting from conception and pregnancy. The exposome promotes a fundamental shift in studying environmental impacts on health, moving research from the classical bio-medical model ‘one exposure, one disease’ to a more comprehensive approach upon which to build solid, cost-effective preventive actions and policies for the future. The nine Projects formalized in the European Human Exposome Network collaboration, throughout referred to as “the Network”, address issues such as exposures to air pollutants, noise, chemicals and urbanisation, in their social context, and their health impacts.

2. Objectives

In order to maximize the impacts of EU exposome research, the Projects in the Network will implement effective communication and dissemination plans. This document presents the overarching joint Communication and Dissemination Strategy (CDS) related to the Network activities and is primarily aimed at external communication. It aims to complement and streamline project-specific communication and dissemination plans that are dedicated to communicating, disseminating and in some cases exploiting project-specific activities. The Network CDS is a dynamic strategy which will be updated regularly (every 12 months, in conjunction with every second Working Group (WG) meeting) (see below) and submitted as an updated deliverable in month 36.

The overarching aim of the Network CDS is to create maximum visibility, awareness and impact for the Network, over and above those that can be achieved by individual projects. To achieve this the following specific objectives are formulated:

1. To set up a **working group** (WG) responsible for implementing the Network CDS
2. To implement a **common strategy** for dissemination and communication of Network and Project activities, where relevant, aimed at reaching maximum impact for key (exploitable) results over and above those that can be achieved by the individual projects.

3. To promote **visibility** of the Network, including through the European Human Exposome Network website, logo and visual identity, and through acknowledging the Network's financial support by the EC where relevant.
4. To promote the activities and results of the Network to a large audience of relevant stakeholders, employing a range of **communication and dissemination tools** and translating the comprehensive results of the Network into accessible materials.
5. To develop a **common stakeholder engagement** strategy for the communication and dissemination of Network activities and results, streamlining the project-specific strategies
6. To develop a **virtual exposome toolbox**, linked to the Network website, with an inventory of all tools developed in the projects and links to project-specific toolboxes.

3. Overall Strategy, Working Group Tasks and Implementation Phases (Obj 1 and 2)

Common strategy: The implementation of a **common strategy** for dissemination and communication of Network and project activities is aimed at reaching maximum impact for results over and above those that can be achieved by individual projects.

In order to achieve this, it is essential to:

- identify opportunities for joint communications,
- identify project results that can be jointly disseminated;
- communicate and disseminate using a consistent language and where possible in a consistent format to help stakeholders to easily interpret the collective results,
- identify and share best practice and information,
- engage the relevant end-users of these results,
- develop the joint tools and materials to reach these stakeholders,
- update the European Commission.

In this section we describe the procedures that will be followed to implement the common strategy, whereas subsequent sections describe the Network's approach to tools and materials, stakeholder engagement and toolbox development.

Communication and Dissemination Working Group:

To streamline communication, the Network will set up a working group (WG). The WG is responsible for implementing the Network Communication and Dissemination Strategy. This WG will consist of one or two representatives from each of the nine projects, normally provided by the partner in charge of dissemination activities in the project (Annex 1). In principle, this WG will have a rotating leadership each 15 months (starting with EXPANSE and REMEDIA); at the end of the first period, the WG will discuss the rotating leadership model and decide on whether to rotate or appoint fixed leadership. The WG, composed of the (co) leaders of the dissemination and communication work packages from each project, will meet at regular intervals (as defined in the Terms of Reference -ToR- of the WG) throughout the projects' duration. It will report back to the Network Steering Group according to the agreed ToR.

Tasks of the Communication and Dissemination WG:

1. **Sharing of Communication and Dissemination plans:** Detailed project-specific communication and dissemination plans will be shared within the Network as soon as they have been accepted by the EC Project Officer. The WG will collect these plans and make them available on a login restricted part of the Network website. The main aim would be to optimise Networks communication and dissemination, by sharing best practices, look for efficiency and avoid unnecessary overlap. This point has been discussed at the first WG meeting.
2. **Sharing of stakeholder lists and preparation of Network stakeholders' inventory and engagement strategy:** Projects will share their stakeholder lists at the institutional level with the WG as soon as they become available.
3. **Sharing of stakeholder information from individual projects will be subject to GDPR.** Through a cross-project mapping exercise, the WG will prepare a stakeholder inventory for the Network, which will be updated periodically, as further described under section 6. A stakeholder engagement strategy will be developed (section 6) while accounting for the GDPR requirements for sharing these lists.
4. **Identification of key results for Network dissemination:** Based on the nine projects' individual communication and dissemination plans, the WG will identify a set of key results of relevance for joint dissemination activities, to reach a broader audience.
5. **Identification of the key network messages** for use in communication and dissemination activities. EU-wide days will also be identified and shared, e.g. World Environment Day.
6. **Organisation of events:** The WG will collect information about project-specific dissemination events and share these with the Network where relevant for joint Network activities through the Event page of the Network's website (details in section 5). The WG will also be involved in the organisation of the common events organised by the Network, such as the final public event.
7. **Common reporting on key events and achievements from the nine projects, through the Network's website and newsletters:** Key outputs and events from each project will be posted on the Network's website on a regular basis, in a perspective of providing a global overview of the Network's achievements. The WG will also prepare a newsletter on Network activities which will be distributed at least every 12 months to all Network partners and stakeholders, as further described in section 5. Representatives from each project are responsible for providing the content. The respective WG leaders in each period are responsible for compiling the first draft of this newsletter. The Network newsletter could also directly link to existing news, social media posts from the nine projects.
8. **Preparation of Communication and Dissemination (C&D) tools and materials:** The WG will be responsible for the preparation of the Network C&D tools and materials that are described in section 5, with the exception of the website and visual identity, which will be developed and maintained by the HEAP project.
9. **Social media:** The WG will make recommendations on how to mention their affiliation to the Network in social medias. For instance, collaborators from the 126 research groups involved in the 9 research projects will be advised to use a common hashtag when posting messages on Twitter about their project, or about initiative of one of the Network's working group. Twitter feeds using this hashtag will be displayed on the Network's website. The WG will also make recommendations concerning the use of other social media, if relevant and used by the different projects. Each research project has already planned to dedicate time and resources to the set-up and use of social media channels that are relevant to its specific target audience. In a cost-efficiency perspective, no additional "layer" will be added to promote **the Network**

in social media. However, tools will be put in place in order to aggregate feeds from the different social media accounts on the Network's website ("social wall").

10. Development of the virtual toolbox: The WG will oversee the development of the virtual toolbox for the Network, as described in section 7.

Implementation phases:

The common strategy for dissemination and communication of Network activities will be implemented in three phases: the launch phase (months 1-15), the continuation phase (months 16-45), and the final phase (months 46-60). The following timeline gives an indication of the activities in each phase; activities in the continuation and final phase are indicative and will be adapted according to the needs of the Network. Adaptations will be detailed in the updated Communication and Dissemination Strategy deliverable due in month 36.

Launch phase (months 1-15):

- Sharing of communication and dissemination plans (between month 6 and 12)
- Sharing of stakeholders lists and first stakeholder inventory (Between month 9 and 12)
- Preparation of tools and materials: website (HEAP) and visual identity (month 10)
- Preparation of Network newsletters (month 12)
- First inventory of key (exploitable) results relevant for joint Network dissemination (month 15)
- Inventory of items that will form part of the project-specific toolboxes as a first step towards creating the Network virtual, potentially automated toolbox (month 15)

Continuation phase (months 16-45):

- Update of Network stakeholder inventory (once per year)
- Update and maintenance of tools and materials
- Updated inventory of key (exploitable) results relevant for joint Network dissemination
- Development of stakeholder engagement strategy based on the project C&D plans and key exploitable results
- Continued communication and dissemination of results, focusing on the key (exploitable) results
- Blueprint for development of Network virtual toolbox
- Updated CDS, describing above activities (deliverable month 24)
- Preparation of Network newsletters (month 24, 36)

Final phase (months 46-60):

- Update of Network stakeholder inventory (once per year)
- Update and maintenance of tools and materials
- Updated inventory of key exploitable results relevant for joint Network dissemination
- Implementation of Network virtual toolbox
- Preparation of Network newsletters (month 48, 60)
- Communication and dissemination of final results, focusing on the key exploitable results
- Organisation of final event

4. Visibility, Acknowledgement and Disclaimer (Obj 3)

In order to generate visibility and awareness, an appropriate visual identity will be developed. The visual identity consists of a style guide (colour scheme, fonts, and visual elements such as icons), a "network membership mark" that will be used on communication material (e.g. "Member of European

Human Exposome Network”) and one common PPT slide about the Network. The visual identity will be used in all communication and dissemination activities related to the Network (Report 6, HEAP, M10). Visibility of the Network will further be promoted through the European Human Exposome Network website (Report 6, HEAP, M10), as described below. Communication and dissemination activities by the Network and its separate Projects need to be identifiable as originating from the Network where relevant. This means that the financial support by the EC shall be highlighted by the following statement and EC banner (e.g. on the Network website, on presentations):

“All Projects which are part of the European Human Exposome Network received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreements No: 874627 (EXPANSE), 874662 (HEAP), 874724 (Equal-Life), 874703 (EPHOR), 874739 (LONGITOOLS), 874583 (ATHLETE), 874864 (HEDIMED), 874753 (REMEDIA) and 874707 (EXIMIOUS)”

In addition to funding acknowledgement, communication and dissemination activities need to include the following disclaimer:

“This reflects only the authors’ view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.”, as required by the EC. Communications and dissemination activities that need to feature the funding acknowledgement include:

- Website
- Presentation templates
- Newsletter
- Reports and briefings
- Videos
- Larger infographics and shareable images
- Event invitations and save-the-dates

Communication materials that do not need to feature the funding acknowledgement (e.g. due to space limitations) include:

- Social media materials such as quote cards, visuals
- Press releases if/when shared by individual groups

5. Communication and Dissemination Tools and Materials (Obj 4)

The following tools and materials will be used for Network specific communication and dissemination in order to reach a wide range of stakeholders (section 6):

Website: The European Human Exposome Network website (Report 6, HEAP, M10), is available at www.humanexposome.eu, which links to the Networks nine individual project’ websites and can be used as point of reference for the entire Network. The website aims at extending awareness of the results of the Network at the broadest possible international scale. All communication material supports will be downloadable from the site (press releases, publishable executive summaries, posters and publications, electronic newsletters, etc.).

Each Project will be responsible for delivery of news and event items and other Project specific information as well as items that might be of interest from a Network perspective, including social media feeds and dissemination of results in published papers. The HEAP-Project will maintain and update the website throughout the duration of the project.

The Network website will link to the individual websites and vice versa. The Launch Event section links to the presentations that were given during the event by key note speakers and the project coordinators. In addition to social media and news feeds the network website will be updated at least every 12 months and the project coordinators and WG members can make suggestions for materials worthwhile publishing. The WG will make the final decisions in close collaboration with HEAP, who hosts the website. It will be considered to create specific sections targeted at different stakeholder groups. It will be considered to record a short video in which the project coordinators explain what their projects are about e.g. in a professional interview.

Network newsletter A network newsletter will be published on a regular basis (at least every 12 months) and will be prepared by the WG members. The newsletter is aimed at an external audience. Target groups should hereby be distinguished, including umbrella organisations, such as Local Governments for Sustainability ICLEI, Healthy cities. The content of the newsletters will cover a review the main news and information of the past period:

- An overview of the main results, key exploitation results (Ker's) and publications with a summary of the potential implications/implementations of the scientific results targeted at stakeholders,
- Conferences, online events, meetings,
- Success stories (e.g. collaboration between projects, progress of working groups),
- Presentation of the coordinating team,
- Individual project reports, events, materials with title and a link to the respective website,
- Journal publications of papers from projects or related exposome results – with two- line explainer on conclusions and relevant public policy implications,
- Focus on the rotating leadership projects each time.

Templates for presentation: One standard PowerPoint slide related to the Network will be made available on the Network website (HEAP M10) and will be used by all projects to communicate the purpose of the Network in a consistent way. Projects should always ensure that the EU H2020 credit/disclaimer is included in any presentation related to the Network. This disclaimer will be part of the template.

Social Media: All network activities and outputs will be disseminated through the hashtag #exposome, rather than creating a handle account. Proactive dissemination of the network activities and goals and advancement of the results from the participating Projects is being done via the EC Twitter hashtag #exposome rather than via the Network. The Twitter flow from #exposome is embedded in the network's website (<https://www.humanexposome.eu/news-all/>) meaning all posts for this hashtag will also be immediately shown on this website, as well as on (@EUScienceInnov and EU_H2020).

The Network will link on the website to social media from the individual nine Projects or via existing networks, Instagram and LinkedIn channels (see Annex 2), of the different members of the consortia rather than support specific Network media. Related initiatives might also be linked up with/followed, in order to maximise communication of relevant information.

Press releases, media articles, etc.: Press releases and media articles from the different participating projects will be shared when considered relevant for the Network. The Network will create its own press releases where relevant for joint activities, e.g. for the final event. Local copies of the Network press releases will be released by the media teams at each coordinating Institute. The Network will engage different stakeholders as outlined in section 6 below.

Conferences, seminars: Individual researchers from the participating Projects will seek maximum exposure for the Network at high profile conferences and seminars. The WG will oversee identifying

joint conferences between projects (resulting from each project communication and dissemination plan) and listing the main conferences in with projects will potentially be involved in and present. Where possible the Network should be referred to, using the standard presentation slide, when presenting at high profile conferences and seminars.

Publications: Joint publications are envisaged such as a special issue introducing the Network in the first year.

Network events: In line with the joint kick-off event (Launch Event) held in February 2020, in year 5 a final joint and public event will be organized by the nine projects. Three network project meetings are also foreseen in months 15, 30 and 45, for network members only.

Common educational messages: The Network's website includes a page that provides a basic definition of the Exposome. This will evolve in a common repository of educational messages about the exposome.

Detailed project specific communication and dissemination plans will be available at different moments in time and tailored for the different Projects. These include stakeholder meetings, workshops and training session. Where relevant and feasible, details will be made available of those events to all researchers within the Network.

6. Stakeholder Engagement (Obj 5)

The Network will focus more on the European level stakeholders that cut across projects, not so much on local/national stakeholders. Exchange of information about key stakeholders at this level will be at the level of institutions rather than individuals, while accounting for GDPR requirements.

Given the scope of exposome research and of the nine Projects collectively, the audience for communication and dissemination of Network-related activities and findings is potentially large and diverse. Effective stakeholder engagement will be crucial to achieving impacts as a Network, over and above the stand-alone projects.

The nine projects that form the Network will each develop their own strategies for stakeholder engagement; these will be detailed in project specific communication and dissemination plans. To streamline stakeholder engagement between projects, the Communication and Dissemination WG, with representatives from each Project, will be responsible for developing a stakeholder engagement strategy.

Mapping Network stakeholders: Given the different research topics of the projects, stakeholder lists are likely to diverge across projects, but it is also likely that there is a set of stakeholders common to several of the projects within the Network. These would mainly be the stakeholders that operate at national or European level, rather than specific local stakeholders. The WG will ask the projects to share an overview of their stakeholders, while accounting for the GDPR requirements for sharing these lists. Through a cross-project mapping exercise, an inventory of stakeholders relevant for Network-level communication and dissemination will then be prepared, also adding stakeholders that are unique to the Network rather than to specific projects. This inventory will form the groundwork for a more efficient approach to the communication and dissemination of Network related activities and results and prevent the same stakeholder from being approached multiple times for involvement. The updated Network CDS (report 7, month 36) will present the stakeholder inventory, as well as a mapping of expected key exploitable results that are relevant for dissemination, end users of these results, and dissemination/communication tools to achieve maximum impact. Examples of stakeholder groups that are expected to be relevant include: Exposome research communities, European-level health communities, national governments across Europe, European Union

institutions, international organisations, media outlets and social media influencers and industry. The main emphasis will be on fostering communication and dissemination on implementation of the results and policy, derived from each of the individual projects. Stakeholders will be identified and selected accordingly.

Stakeholder engagement strategy for the Network: Much can be learned by exchanging information on how to interact with stakeholders. The WG will exchange experiences and strategies related to stakeholder engagement from the nine Projects, with the ultimate aim of establishing similar practices across Projects and developing a stakeholder engagement strategy for the Network. This strategy will be presented in the updated CDS (report 7, month 36), after careful examination of the Project specific Communication and Dissemination Plans.

7. Development of a Virtual Toolbox (Obj 6)

The Projects that make up the European Human Exposome Network each responded to the call text (Call SC1-BHC-28-2019), which included the development of a toolbox both in the title (“The Human Exposome Project: a toolbox for assessing and addressing the impact of environment on health”) and in the expected impacts (“Enabling researchers and policy makers to continuously include new knowledge in the policy making processes by using the toolbox to generate data and information”).

The nine projects have thus in common that they will develop a toolbox and make this available to researchers and policy makers outside the Projects and beyond the lifespan of the Projects. Toolbox contents are specific to each project, but may include, for example, database and results catalogues, data collection protocols, analysis pipelines and protocols, health impact assessment and intervention toolkits, e-learning tutorials, and policy recommendations.

It is recognised across the Network that it will be important to build an **inventory of tools** developed in all Projects, in order to avoid that stakeholders wishing to find certain tools would have to search nine separate toolboxes.

This tool inventory or “virtual toolbox” will be available on the Network website and will allow users to search through the tools, using an easy-to-use classification of tools. Links to the location of each tool, as well as a brief explanation of its use, will be included.

The development of this virtual toolbox will take place in several steps and will be overseen by the Communication and Dissemination WG:

- in the *launch phase* a list of expected project specific toolboxes items will be assembled, and the Network website will flag the expected contents of the virtual toolbox;
- in the *continuation phase*, a blueprint for the virtual toolbox will be developed, mapping project-specific items to wider toolbox topic areas and developing procedures for its implementation on the website;
- in the *final phase*, the virtual toolbox will be implemented on the Network website.

The development of the virtual toolbox will work closely with other relevant Network working groups, e.g. metadata WG and the statistics WG.

Annex 1: List of WG members

Communication WG EXPOSOME projects			
Project	Name	Organisation	Role
Equal Life	Peter van den Hazel	INCHES	Leader work package on CDE
Equal Life	Miriam Weber	City of Utrecht	Deputy Leader work package on CDE
Longitools	Johanne Boulding	Beta	Leader work package on CDE
Longitools	Claire Webster	Beta	Deputy Leader work package on CDE
Expanse	Jelle Vlaanderen	IRAS University Utrecht	Co-coordinator Project
Expanse	Martje Ebberink	IRAS University Utrecht	Coordinator Communication & Dissemination
HEAP	Dominique Meunier	IARC	Deputy Leader work package on CDE
HEAP	Anouk Berger	IARC	Deputy Leader work package on CDE
HEAP	Heather Coombs	IARC	Deputy Leader work package on CDE
HEDIMED	Olli Laitinen	Tampere University	CSO
HEDIMED	Rainer Thiel	Empirica	Leader work package on CDE
HEDIMED	Administration	Tampere University	Administration
EPHOR	Luuk van Wel	TNO	Responsible for EPHOR Toolbolx
EPHOR	Rob Stierum	TNO	Co-coordinator /scientific support
ATHLETE	Genon Jensen	HEAL	Leading work package on CDE
ATHLETE	ivonne Leenen	HEAL	Deputy leader
REMEDIA	Sophie Lanone	INSERM	Coordinator REMEDIA
REMEDIA	Manon Bendjir	INSERM	Leader work package on CDE
EXIMIOUS	Emily Ciscato	accelopment	Leader work package on CDE
EXIMIOUS	Julia Götz	accelopment	Co- Leader work package on CDE

Annex 2: List of social media channels

Overview of communication channels for the nine EU Human Exposome Projects				
Project	Website	Twitter	Facebook	LinkedIn
ATHLETE	https://www.env-health.org/athlete/	#ATHLETEproject	No*	No
EXIMIOUS	https://www.eximious-h2020.eu/	@EXIMIOUS_H2020	https://www.facebook.com/Eximious_h2020-110211130543598/	https://www.linkedin.com/groups/13827565/
EXPANSE	https://expansoproject.eu/	No	No	No
EPHOR	https://www.ephor-project.eu/	No	No	https://www.linkedin.com/company/ephor-project-eu/
EQUAL-LIFE	https://www.equal-life.eu/en	https://twitter.com/EquallifeEU	No	No
HEAP	http://heap-exposome.eu/	Partner Accounts	No	No
HEDIMED	https://www.hedimed.eu/	@HEDIMED2020	No	No
LONGITOOLS	https://longitools.org/	@LongITools	No	No
REMEDIA	https://h2020-remedia.eu/	@H2020Remedia	No	No

*No: Partner Accounts

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